

Sectoral brief

November 2025

Reducing Risks Together: Multi-hazards and multi-risks in the food and agriculture sector

Executive summary & Recommendations

Multi-risks and multi-hazards are already a determining factor in European agricultural losses. The EUCRA report (EEA, 2024) identifies food and water security as critical risks; the 2022 drought caused significant declines in maize, soybean and sunflower harvests; the 2023 floods in Emilia-Romagna demonstrated prolonged secondary effects. Climate change intensifies the frequency and severity of “multi-hazard events” (e.g. drought + heatwave; winter storm + flooding + landslides) which translate into “multi-risks” for production, quality, soils, water, plant health, logistics and markets. Assessing single threats underestimates the impact and fails to capture temporal dependencies (e.g., dry soils amplify heat damage, or saturated watersheds exacerbate cascading floods, and increased large-scale forest fires).

Recent scientific studies provide further evidence that climate change is altering the frequency, intensity and coincidence of extreme events across Europe. The assessment of multi-risks in Europe in the context of climate change shows that an increase in compound sequences of drought and flooding is expected, underscoring the importance of systemic risk management. The quantification of multi-risks due to climate change requires a quantitative framework for estimating the probability of simultaneous and consecutive extreme events, such as heat waves coinciding with droughts during critical growth stages of major Mediterranean

crops. For the food and agriculture sector, studies highlight the need to incorporate composite probability assessments into crop modelling, irrigation planning and insurance plans, especially in warming scenarios of more than 2 °C. In 2022, Europe suffered widespread drought with yield reductions, particularly in maize, sunflower and soybeans; in 2023, flooding in Emilia-Romagna affected thousands of farms, damaging woody and herbaceous crops and causing multimillion-Euro losses. The EUCRA report warns that numerous risks, including food security, have reached critical levels and could become catastrophic without urgent action.

This document demonstrates how knowledge developed in the MYRIAD-EU project can be used in the food and agriculture sector, including harmonised definitions of multi-hazard/multi-risk, sets of historical events (MYRIAD-HES), and a multi-sectoral perspective (energy-water-ecosystems-transport-finance-agriculture and food). The MYRIAD-EU project tested its approaches in five Pilots (Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands) to co-develop Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) pathways.

Recommendations:

- **Governance and planning:** Integrate climate and soil indicators and crop phenology into agricultural and water planning, using MYRIAD-HES to identify multi-risk zones and guide territorial and varietal diversification.
- **Tools, data and modelling:** Apply composite heat-drought indices in crop models, combining sensors and satellite data for irrigation, early warnings, and systemic risk assessment.

- **Water and soil management:** Modernise irrigation, improve water efficiency, and use green infrastructure to enhance infiltration and retention.
- **Plant health and biodiversity:** Implement integrated pest management and conserve functional biodiversity.
- **Varieties and diversification:** Adapt crops and calendars, diversify spatially and altitudinally, and explore agrovoltatics.
- **Economy and insurance:** Provide coverage for chain events, contingency funds, and farmer training in resilient practices.

Context

European evidence confirms the co-occurrence of hazards (e.g., wind + winter flooding) and the increase in heatwave-drought episodes; impacts spread across sectors (energy, transport, water) and throughout food and agriculture chains.

Operational frameworks often address single threats, but agroclimatic risks result from combined hazards, their sequence, and local vulnerabilities (phenology, soil moisture, infrastructure, markets). In north-western Europe, storms and floods are linked; in the Mediterranean, heat and drought increasingly coincide, harming crops such as maize, wheat, olive, vine and fruit trees. Spain's 2025 drought-fire crisis burned over 393,000 ha, caused seven deaths and mass evacuations. EDORA reported drought across one-third of Europe, with severe impacts on food and agriculture.

MYRIAD-EU responds by promoting a systemic, multi-risk and multi-sector approach, supported by tools like MYRIAD-HES. The project develops disaster risk reduction pathways in five pilot regions (Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands), analysing trade-offs across several sectors: energy, ecosystems, finance, food & agriculture, tourism, and transport. Funded by Horizon 2020 (2021–2025), it aims to drive a paradigm shift in risk management.

Figure 1; Relative occurrence of selected compound hazards under current vs. +2 °C climates. Adapted from recent multi-hazard assessments. EUCRA report (EEA, 2024)

MYRIAD-EU developed a handbook of definitions (Gill et al., 2022), and the wiki portal [Disaster Risk Gateway](#), which are excellent resources for us to get common language and definitions related to multi-hazards and multi-risk. It also developed a systemic approach, assessing trade-offs and synergies between sectors. For the food and agriculture sector, this involves quantifying the multi-risk at the basin-farm-value chain scale, integrating climatic, hydrological and agronomic data sources and linking it to finance and insurance. Several key lessons are: (1) precisely defining multi-hazard/multi-risk to ensure comparability; (2) making temporal dependence explicit (soil water memory, lag between storms, post-flood/frost recovery); (3) monetising direct and indirect losses; (4) co-designing DRR pathways with public and private actors in each pilot/territory; and (5) assessing possible climate change mitigation and resilience actions tailored to each specific territory.

Applications of MYRIAD-EU results

Climate Extremes Affecting European Agriculture

Aspect	Rising Temperatures & Droughts	Heavy Precipitation & Flooding	Droughts & Forest Fires
Definition	Long-lasting dry periods disrupting hydrological balance; types: meteorological, agricultural, hydrological.	Short, intense rainfall exceeding infiltration/ drainage, leading to floods, erosion, landslides.	Soil moisture deficits combined with heat/wind, increasing fire danger and agroecosystem instability.
Key Facts	2022: major drought, yield losses in maize/ soybean/sunflower. Rising probability of heat-drought co-occurrence. +2 °C → unprecedented stress for maize.	2023 Emilia-Romagna: record rainfall, 300+ landslides, €1.5B agricultural losses. Compound flood events rising in Central & Southern Europe.	2022: worst drought in 500 years + 785,000 ha burned. 2023: record wildfire in Greece. 2025: widespread drought + fires in Spain, Italy, Greece.
Recent Observations	2022: maize (-16%), soybean (-15%), sunflower (-12%). Spain 2023: olive -40%. EU viticulture losses. UK 2023-25: warmest/driest → cereal, vegetable, milk, fodder decline; beef farmers hit hardest.	Germany/Belgium 2021 floods destroyed farmland. Emilia-Romagna 2023: orchards, vineyards, horticulture hit; root asphyxia, tree mortality, erosion. Spain & France: floods in coastal/river basins reduced cereal & vegetable output.	Spain/Portugal 2022: vineyards, olives, cereals lost to wildfires. France 2022: smoke taint in vineyards. Italy/Greece 2023: orchards, pastures burned → livestock feed shortage. Spain 2025: olives, vineyards, fruit orchards damaged; smoke taint & defoliation.
Projections	At +2 °C (late 2030s): maize faces unprecedented stress; drought = main loss driver in maize, variable in wheat. CO ² benefits will not offset water/heat stress.	With +2 °C warming: compound storm-flood events could double in Po, Danube, Rhine. Greater crop losses, fungal outbreaks, delayed harvests.	+2 °C: Mediterranean severe drought frequency doubles; 30-50% more fire danger days; longer fire season. More compound heat-drought-fire events threatening perennials & agroforestry.
Agronomic Implications	Irrigation mitigates but limited by water/energy. Need irrigation modernisation, water reuse, natural retention. Woody crops: reduced reserves, higher mortality. Herbaceous: accelerated phenology, poor pollination/ grain filling, higher pests.	Floods cause yield losses via root asphyxia, nutrient leaching, erosion. Woody crops: less resilience, higher pathogens. Herbaceous: lower quality, mycotoxin risk. Need drainage, NWRM, floodplain management.	Water stress, mortality, direct fire damage. Soil degradation after fires (erosion, hydrophobic layers). Quality: smoke taint in grapes, lower olive oil content, forage shortage. Need efficient irrigation, crop diversification, soil conservation, fire-risk integration.

Policy and governance (EU and regional): frameworks for operationalising the multi- risk approach

- EUCRA (EEA, 2024)**: 36 climate risks, with food and water security as priorities; calls for urgent action.
- Regulation (EU) 2020/741**: reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation with minimum requirements, risk management and transparency; key to mitigating droughts.
- Natural Water Retention Measures (NWRM)**: multi-benefit instrument to mitigate floods, water scarcity, and improve ecological status; aligned with WFD and Floods Directive.
- Regional framework (e.g., Extremadura)**: integrated crop production (cherry, tomato, paprika, olive, etc.), nitrate-vulnerable areas, and irrigation efficiency/environmental programmes (REDAREX/RECAEX) with fertigation and runoff control guidelines.

Practical implication – Combining 2020/741 (reuse) + NWRM + integrated production and nitrates increases water resilience and reduces diffuse post-event pollution.

Applications of MYRIAD-EU results

One of the barriers to incorporating a multi-risk perspective into the food and agriculture sector is the lack of clear definitions, which are essential for understanding how these events can affect the sector. Although the effects of climate change risks are long-term, therefore requiring actions dedicated to adapting to climate change, these actions are mainly focused on maintaining the profitability and variability of agricultural operations. DRR actions should also aim at implementing strategies that allow adaptation to adverse phenomena that are already causing problems in crop productivity and, therefore, in their marketing and food availability. These actions should be aimed at developing decision-

making systems for each situation that allow for a wide range of solutions adapted to each specific situation (e.g. drought, heat waves and floods), which can be modelled but are very difficult to predict and require rapidly implementable risk contingency plans. The development of these actions for each risk situation and the possible actions aimed at mitigating them will be based on the experience of the effects of risks on different areas, using databases and experience. For DRR actions, we would turn to the academic world for information.

MYRIAD-EU developed a **Handbook** (Gill et al., 2022) that sets out terminological and conceptual foundations for the multi-hazard risk management approach adopted by MYRIAD-EU. It is an excellent resource for us to get these definitions, with the added benefit that there are definitions from multiple industry sectors and academic views. This provides context to the definitions as well as an understanding of the potential applicability, or limitations, of the definitions to the food and agriculture sector. Its most relevant contributions to the food and agriculture sector are:

- **Glossary of ‘multi-hazard’ and ‘multi-risk’ terms:** It establishes precise definitions for complex phenomena such as compound risks, direct and indirect impacts, exposure and vulnerability, which are fundamental for interpreting situations where droughts, fires or floods simultaneously affect agriculture.
- **Proposed multi-risk indicators:** The manual offers an initial set of indicators aimed at diagnosing and monitoring multi-risks—including their interrelated nature – which is essential for assessing threats such as the combination of drought and fires on crops, pastures or agricultural soils.
- **Integrated and cross-cutting perspective:** The need to move beyond isolated sectoral approaches is highlighted, favouring a systemic vision that links food and agriculture, with other sectors like infrastructure, ecosystems and governance. This approach is key to assessing how a hazard that has agricultural effects can trigger chain effects

(e.g. loss of production, soil degradation, disruption of supply chains).

- **Application to real contexts (pilots):** The manual supports the use of these definitions and indicators in applied pilot studies, where the food and agriculture sector can be assessed against multi-hazard scenarios, allowing for a more accurate characterisation of its exposure, vulnerability and adaptive capacities.

- The MYRIAD Hazard Event Sets Algorithm (**MYRIAD-HESA**; Claassen et al., 2023) is an algorithm designed to compile global databases of combined multi-hazard events – crucial for understanding how threats overlap and their impact on agriculture. It offers a robust tool for identifying and quantifying the frequency of various multi-hazard events, as well as a comprehensive global view with the multi-hazards and multi-risks MYRIAD-Hazard Event Sets Dataset (MYRIAD-HES). Some key elements are: Multi-hazard coverage: It includes multiple types of hazards (meteorological, climatic, hydrological, geological), such as droughts, forest fires, floods, heat waves, etc., allowing for analysis of their concurrence and temporal proximity.

- **Time dimension (time-lag):** Captures events that do not occur at the same time, but in rapid succession, allowing for the identification of consecutive hazards (e.g., a drought followed by a fire)—especially relevant for understanding how such events impact crops or agroforestry systems.

- **Global historical database (2004–2017):** Provides objective and systematised evidence on frequency, combination of hazards and critical areas. These data are useful for constructing risk models in the food and agriculture sector, anticipating events such as heatwaves followed by fires or floods after droughts.

- **Open and scalable:** As it is freely accessible, the MYRIAD-HESA methodology allows for regional or sectoral adaptations, such as building specific event sets for European agriculture, adapted to spatial and temporal resolutions relevant to crops and rural areas.

The MYRIAD-EU pilots are living laboratories

where multiple risk management tools, methods, and approaches are tested and adapted from a multi-sectoral perspective. For the food and agriculture sector, they represent a unique opportunity to:

- Develop resilient strategies against multi-hazard events (e.g. droughts, fires, floods, and their interactions).
- Transfer effective solutions between agricultural regions with similar challenges.
- Strengthen institutional, technical and cooperative capacities to anticipate and reduce extreme climate risks.

These lessons are fundamental to moving towards more robust food and agriculture systems in contexts of increasing climate variability and uncertainty.

Each pilot integrates at least three key sectors from among: **food & agriculture, ecosystems & forestry, infrastructure & transport, energy, finance and tourism**. In all of them, the pilot acts as a real laboratory to:

- Co-develop multi-hazard, multi-sector and systemic risk management frameworks with local stakeholders.
- Experiment with proactive and resilient management strategies in the face of extreme composite events such as floods, droughts, fires and desertification, among others.
- Among the five pilots, the following specifically address the food and agriculture sector:
 - **Canary Islands:** combines geological (earthquakes, volcanoes) and hydrometeorological risks with a high dependence on tourism and local food and agriculture supply.
 - **Scandinavia:** incorporates risks such as forest fires, drought, floods and heat, together with the food and agriculture sector and ecosystems, which makes it easier to analyse how these shocks affect agricultural and forestry production

- **Danube Basin:** addresses drought, floods and other hazards in a region with high agricultural, infrastructure and transport interdependence; this allows for the mapping of cross-sectoral impacts (e.g. how floods affect crops and logistics networks).

The integration of these tools and pilots can:

- **Facilitate the analysis of the food and agriculture sector** under complex, realistic and empirically grounded multi-risk scenarios.
- **Enable the design of warning systems, policies** and adaptive strategies specifically geared towards the food and agriculture sector.
- **Build capacity for researchers, risk managers and agricultural decision-makers** to assess the impact of combined events, optimise resources and prioritise measures in the face of events that are potentially devastating for crops and food chains.

Applied regional examples (MYRIAD-EU pilots in the food and agriculture sector)

Canary Islands – Drought + Fires + Food dependency

In 2023–2024, the Canary Islands experienced prolonged droughts combined with heat waves that fuelled forest fires in Tenerife and Gran Canaria. These affected vineyards and subtropical fruit trees (avocado, banana). The cascading risk resulted in water shortages, loss of local production and increased dependence on imports, increasing logistical vulnerability. Priority measures include the use of reclaimed and desalinated water (EU Regulation 2020/741), diversification towards heat- and drought-tolerant crops, and the design of multi-risk insurance for fruit trees and banana plantations.

Figure 1; Canary Islands - precipitation and temperature anomalies (2015–2024).

Scandinavia – Wind + Winter flooding + Emerging agriculture

In recent winters, Atlantic storms with extreme winds and heavy rainfall have caused flooding in agricultural areas of Denmark and southern Sweden. Affected crops: winter cereals and potatoes, with problems of root asphyxia, erosion and nutrient loss. Warming is expanding the area suitable for cultivation northwards (cereals, rapeseed, fodder crops), but increasing the risk of emerging pests. Adaptation measures include the implementation of NWRM (wetlands, hedges), the use of waterlogging-resistant varieties, and early warning systems for spreading pests.

Veneto – Torrential rains + Landslides + Viticulture

The torrential rains of 2023 in Emilia-Romagna had parallels in Veneto, affecting vineyards on slopes and vegetables. The multi-hazard manifested itself in erosion and landslides that damaged agricultural infrastructure and grape quality, with high replanting costs. Key measures include controlled drainage, natural barriers on vineyard slopes, agrovoltaic systems to mitigate insolation, and varietal diversification towards grapes with greater tolerance to compound events.

Danube region – Extreme droughts + Heat waves

The extreme drought of 2022 in the Danube region, combined with heat waves, drastically reduced maize and sunflower yields (up to -30% in Hungary and Romania). Low river levels affected river transport of cereals, making logistics more expensive. This cascading risk combined production and logistical losses with market pressure. Measures include modernising irrigation with sensors and efficient fertigation, multi-risk insurance for cereals, and NWRM at the basin scale (restoration of floodplains, wetlands) to improve water retention.

Figure 2. Danube - Water deficit and maize and sunflower yields (2010-2022).

In the Danube basin, the combination of heat and drought appears in MYRIAD-HES as highly correlated, allowing for projected increases in maize and sunflower losses under +2 °C scenarios. In contrast, in Scandinavia, the wind+flooding pairs show greater relevance in winter, with implications for winter cereals and potatoes. This spatial differentiation of correlations allows for the orientation of both regional policies (irrigation and multi-risk insurance in the Danube) and logistical and drainage adaptation strategies in Scandinavia.

Figure 5. Multi-hazard pairs relevant to food and agriculture and their relative frequency. Based on Claassen et al. (2023).

Recommendations

Governance and planning

- Integrate composite indicators (SPI/SSI, accumulated heat, soil moisture) and phenological thresholds by crop into the CAP and water management plans.
- Multiple risk assessment: adopt the definitions and taxonomy of the MYRIAD-EU Handbook to classify composite and multiple risks, ensuring a multi-risk perspective.
- Multi-risk zoning by basin based on MYRIAD-HES; prioritise natural water resource management and soft overflow areas with compensation.
- Update regulations on fertigation and runoff/leaching control with a multi-risk approach. Adjust fertiliser levels based on phenology and consider all components of the balance.

Tools, data and modelling

- Adopt MYRIAD-EU definitions; document temporal dependencies and post-event cascading effects.
- Crop modelling: integrate composite indices (heat + drought) into models (e.g. DSSAT/ APSIM) and insurance assessments; use plant and soil indicators (microtensiometers, soil moisture) and remote sensing (SMOS/ Sentinel) for irrigation scheduling.
- Incorporate multiple risks into harvest models and insurance rates; create coverage for “chain events”.
- Deploy multi-risk early warning systems with soil-plant-atmosphere sensors and EO. Combine sub-seasonal/seasonal forecasts with sensors and EO for critical phenological windows. Establish early warning networks for flood control (e.g. the Spida network in Extremadura).
- Systemic risk: combine water-energy-logistics modules (e.g. river restrictions) to quantify indirect losses.

Water and soil management

- Modernise irrigation (sectorisation, variable pressure) and prioritise reclaimed water under Directive 2020/741; audit water efficiency at the basin and farm level.
- Green infrastructure: roofs, buffer strips, agroforestry, reduced tillage and organic amendments to increase infiltration and retention.

Plant health and functional biodiversity

- Integrated pest management in extreme weather conditions: monitoring, dynamic thresholds, biological control and inoculum reduction after flooding. Assess the effect of stress situations on increased plant vulnerability to existing and new pests.
- Ecological corridors and hedges to maintain natural enemies and reduce population peaks after warm winters/heat waves.

Varieties, calendars and diversification

- Heat/drought-tolerant genetic material; adjustment of sowing/harvesting to sub-seasonal forecasts; spatial/altitudinal diversification.
- Agrovoltatics in heat-stress-sensitive crops (vineyards, horticulture), with microclimatic and water benefits (shading during periods of high temperature). Protection against frost and hail.

Economy, insurance and just transition

- Coverage and reinsurance for chain events and quality losses; contingency funds for "long tails" (replanting, woody crops).
- Incentives and training for small farms in irrigation technologies and resilient practices.

List of resources

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